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Impact Of Fiscal Discipline And Pension Policies On Retired Civil Servants' Socioeconomic Well-Being In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of fiscal discipline and pension fund management policies on the socioeconomic well-being of retired civil servants in Rivers State, and it is anchored on the General System Theory. Testing a hypothesis, and utilizing a survey method, primary data were collected through questionnaires and interviews with pension administrators, retirees, and policymakers, while secondary data were obtained from government publications, journal articles, textbooks, and other relevant sources. The findings indicate that pension administrators often lack proper accountability, resulting in irregular payments, and that procedural challenges such as bureaucratic delays, dishonesty, and weak oversight critically undermine pension management effectiveness. These issues negatively affect retirees' welfare. Based on these insights, the study recommends strengthening regulatory oversight, investing in modern digital systems, enhancing stakeholder engagement, eliminating political interference, promoting transparency and accountability, encouraging savings, and fostering investor confidence. Implementing these strategies could significantly improve the socioeconomic conditions of retirees and contribute to more sustainable pension management in Rivers State.

Keywords: pension management, civil servants, socioeconomic welfare, policy effectiveness, accountability, digital systems, stakeholder engagement

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of pension and gratuity as retirement benefits in Nigeria's public service began in 1951, recognizing the social and economic contributions of government employees (Ajie, 2014). These benefits serve as motivation tools aimed at enhancing the socioeconomic welfare of retirees, especially since many retirees' personal savings and investments may not suffice to sustain a reasonable standard of living after retirement (Oladipo, Fashagba & Akindele, 2022). Over the years, retirement and pension management have become critical issues, attracting the attention of governments, employers, and workers across Nigeria and many other developing countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (Ajie, 2014).

In most advanced nations, effective pension schemes form an essential part of the social insurance system; these systems are designed so that retirees can live comfortably on their pensions without destabilizing their families' economic stability. Nwanna and Ogbonna (2019, p. 23) describe pension schemes as government-initiated techniques intended to motivate workers and boost productivity during employment before retirement. However, in Nigeria, the pension system has faced significant challenges,

primarily due to deficiencies in service delivery despite the increasing number of pensionable public sector employees (Negbe & Egobueze, 2021). Many African countries have undergone reforms in public service to improve efficiency, driven by structural adjustment programs and the movement towards new public management models in the 1980s.

The rising financial demands of pension liabilities, such as addressing accrued pension debts, have necessitated reforms over time in Nigeria (Ngo, Egobueze & Nwaoburu, 2024). Nonetheless, pension planning remains fraught with challenges globally, and Nigeria is no exception. Workers often face low incomes and savings, compounded by substantial family and social responsibilities, which complicate retirement planning. The average life expectancy in Nigeria is around 54 years, but many Nigerians live up to 80 or 90 years, exacerbating the strain on pension systems and individual planning (Ngo, Egobueze & Nwaoburu, 2024).

The inefficiency of Nigeria's pension arrangements has led to a decline in workers' confidence in the system, prompting many to seek alternative ways to secure their future. Adams (2015) argues that the Pension Reform Act of 2004, which introduced contributory schemes, has been largely ineffective in restoring trust. Many workers continue to support their relatives financially, often at the expense of their pension benefits, and some resort to corrupt practices to meet future needs (Crowther & Seifi, 2011).

To address these issues, the Nigerian government enacted the Pension Reform Act of 2004, which aimed to overhaul the pension system and reduce the financial burden on the government (Agba, 2018). The Act mandates that both public and private sector employers with five or more employees contribute 7.5% of each employee's salary into a Retirement Savings Account (RSA). Additionally, the military contributes 2.5%, while the government contributes 12.5% on behalf of military personnel (Pension Reform Act, 2004). The primary goal of this reform was to encourage individuals to save for their retirement, thereby reducing reliance on government funds and ensuring financial security in old age (Adegbayi, 2015).

Despite the reform, many workers remain anxious about their retirement, largely because the scheme overlooks psychological preparedness. Ahmad (2015, 2018) notes that many retirees experience worries and anxieties about their post-retirement life, which affects their overall satisfaction. Retirement impacts not only financial stability but also psychological and social well-being, including health, status, recognition, and social relationships (Alemu, 2015). The emotional stress resulting from these factors can influence retirees' mental health and social interactions, making psychological preparedness critical.

Retirement is a significant life transition that requires careful preparation. Ahmad (2016) emphasizes that life does not stop at retirement; individuals must adjust to new routines and identities, often experiencing a sense of loss of purpose and status. Proper psychological preparation involves organizing pre-retirement educational programs that impart vital knowledge, skills, and emotional intelligence to help individuals transition successfully. These skills include self-efficacy, assertiveness, critical thinking, and emotional resilience, which can foster a smoother transition and improved life satisfaction.

Globally, retirement is a complex phenomenon that involves multiple transitions. Amujuri (2009) explains that the shift from work to non-work life is particularly demanding due to inadequate preparation, leading to stress and anxiety. Retirement is often viewed as a period of freedom, free from work pressures, but it also brings challenges such as reduced income, loss of occupational identity, and the need to fill leisure time meaningfully (Petkoska & Earl, 2019). The transition can be difficult, especially if individuals are unprepared psychologically or financially.

In Nigeria, and specifically in Rivers State, retirement issues are increasingly prominent among scholars, policymakers, and practitioners. The government's focus on constitutional, administrative, socioeconomic, and political responsibilities often leaves little attention to workers' post-retirement well-being. Consequently, many workers are preoccupied with attaining satisfaction in retirement, often resorting to corruption or other means to secure financial stability, health, social relations, and leisure activities (Ozor, 2016).

In Rivers State, the retirement phenomenon has become a topical issue, creating confusion among state and non-state actors regarding roles and responsibilities. The government's efforts tend to emphasize administrative and political functions, often neglecting the socioeconomic welfare of retirees. As a result,

many workers worry about whether their retirement benefits will be sufficient to support them, especially amid Nigeria's ongoing economic challenges. Concerns about health, social status, and the ability to maintain a decent standard of living after retirement are prevalent, leading to pre-retirement anxiety that can affect workers' performance and productivity even before retirement (Ameh, Ajieh & Duhu, 2021; Ozor, 2016).

The management and administration of pension and gratuity schemes are critical to the socioeconomic well-being of retirees in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State. The effectiveness of pension reforms, workers' psychological preparedness, and the government's commitment to addressing retirees' needs significantly influence retirees' quality of life. As Nigeria continues to grapple with economic and social challenges, improving pension schemes and ensuring comprehensive support for retirees remain vital to fostering social stability and individual dignity in old age.

Based on the foregoing, the study interrogates a question, thus: What is the effectiveness of pension fund management policies on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in General System Theory (GST), developed by Karl Ludwig von Bertalanffy, an Austrian biologist and one of the pioneers of the theory. GST provides a framework for understanding complex societal and organizational patterns by emphasizing holism—viewing systems from parts to whole and vice versa. Unlike a simple collection of components, a system is an active entity with boundaries, structures, and functions, influenced by its environment. Bertalanffy highlighted that changes in one part of a system can impact the entire system, producing predictable behavioral patterns (Ugben & Egobueze, 2021). The outputs of a system result from inputs; the system processes inputs into outputs, much like the human body transforming food and oxygen into waste products. This continuous transformation enables system functionality, and disruptions in one part can destabilize the whole (Ngo, Egobueze & Nwaoburu, 2024).

Applying GST to pension schemes, the entire pension system is viewed as part of the larger economic system. This perspective is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where pension management is a product of a developing economy that increasingly relies on formal pension schemes. The theory helps analyze how pension investments, fund management, and assets like property contribute to economic development and retirees' socioeconomic wellbeing. Pooling pension resources, for example, can reduce risks and lower costs by diversifying investments, thus supporting stable returns and improved welfare for retirees (Negbe & Egobueze, 2021).

Furthermore, GST suggests that pension funds operate as intermediaries influencing economic growth through efficient financial system functions. Pension fund administrators are considered sustainable when they can cover their operational costs from contributions and generate sufficient revenue to support retirees' wellbeing. The development of pension funds follows a lifecycle pattern—beginning with startup, progressing through growth, and reaching maturity—each stage demanding different financing strategies (Ngo, Egobueze & Nwaoburu, 2024). The theory posits that the sources of funding for pension administrators are linked to their developmental stage, which in turn impacts the socioeconomic status of retirees.

The system's effectiveness depends on the interaction and coordination among all components—government agencies, pension managers, regulatory bodies, and beneficiaries. If any part of this network falters, the entire pension system and, consequently, the broader economy could be adversely affected. For instance, inefficiencies or corruption within pension management undermine the system's stability and threaten retirees' financial security. The inability of pension administrators to keep the system functional reflects systemic weaknesses that have plagued pension management in Nigeria, leading to issues such as delayed payments and loss of public trust.

In conclusion, GST provides a comprehensive lens through which to examine pension schemes, emphasizing their interconnectedness within the larger economic and social system. Ensuring the

system’s functionality requires effective management, coordination, and adaptation across all components to sustain retirees’ wellbeing and support national economic development.

METHODOLOGY

The research employed a survey design, integrating both primary and secondary data collection methods, known as triangulation to enhance thoroughness in data gathering and analysis. This approach ensures comprehensive insights by capturing respondents’ views and existing literature, facilitating generalizations from the sample to the broader population.

The population comprised 11,000 individuals, including 10,950 retirees and 50 staff members of the Rivers State Pension Board, covering the period from 2014 to 2024. This figure excludes deceased retirees. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula, resulting in a sample of 386 respondents. Purposive sampling was adopted due to the unequal distribution of retirees across different cadres, selecting specific individuals based on their roles, experience, and background—aiming to meet the study’s specific objectives.

Participants included retirees and pension board staff, categorized into board members, senior cadres, and junior cadres. Questionnaires were distributed accordingly: 178 to junior cadre pensioners, 83 to staff of the Board, and 125 to senior cadre pensioners. The questionnaires were tailored based on participants’ academic background, position, and experience.

Data collection involved primary sources, namely; questionnaires and interviews, while secondary sources such as existing research, journals, articles, textbooks, and online academic resources. The primary data were analyses through tabulation and analysis using SPSS version 23.0, a user-friendly statistical tool suited for the analysis. Hypotheses were tested with the chi-square statistical test at a 0.05 significance level, assessing the difference between observed and expected values. The chi-square formula applied was $\chi^2 = \sum(O_i - E_i)^2/E_i$, with the degrees of freedom calculated as (R-1)(C-1). The decision rule stated that the null hypothesis would be rejected if the chi-square value exceeded the table value, indicating a significant difference in the variables tested.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first section of this work dealt with socio-demographic analysis of administered and returned questionnaires while the second section analysed the responses on fundamental issues raised by the study using mean value followed by test of hypotheses and discussion of findings.

Presentation of Data

Table 1: Socio-demographic Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	386	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	36	9
Number of questionnaires retrieved	350	91
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2025

The table above revealed that out of the 386 questionnaires that were administered to respondents, 36 respondents making 9% of the questionnaires were not returned, 350 respondents representing 91% were successfully completed, retrieved and valid for proper analysis. The response rate is 91% and this is a mark of excellence for the study.

Table 2: Socio-demographic Analysis of Returned/Valid Questionnaires

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency of Questionnaire Distributed	Frequency of Returned Questionnaire	Percentage (%) of Returned Questionnaire
Junior Cadre Pensioners	178	150	84
Staff of the Board	83	80	96
Senior Cadre Pensioners	125	120	96
Total	386	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2025

Data in table 4.2 above revealed that out of the 386 questionnaires, 150 questionnaires were returned out of 178 that were administered to respondents. Also, 80 questionnaires were returned out of 83 that were administered while 120 returned out of 125 questionnaires that were administered to respondents making 84%, 96% and 96% respectively. The response rate of total questionnaires returned is 91% which is a mark of excellence for the study.

Table 3: Socio-demographic Analysis of Gender

Gender of Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	200	57
Female	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 4.3 above showed that 200 respondents representing 57% are male while 150 respondents representing 43% are female. This indicates that the majority of the respondents are male. Irrespective of their genders, their responses do not in any way interfere with the outcomes of the study as they were not biased in their views.

Table 4: Socio-demographic Analysis of Academic Background

Educational Qualifications	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
HND/BSc/PGD	200	57
MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2025

The table above depicted the educational qualifications of respondents and thus revealed that 200 respondents making 57% possess the Higher National Diploma (HND)/Bachelor of Science (BSc) and Postgraduate Diploma (PGD) while 150 respondents representing 43% are holders of Master of Business Administration (MBA)/Master of Public Administration (MPA)/Master of Science (M.Sc) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D). This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge of pension fund management and its effect on the socioeconomic welfare of retirees.

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS

Computation of response rate on the effectiveness of pension fund management policies on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants.

Table 5: Shows Item 1 of Research Question: Pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	95	50	80	225		
Agreed (3)	50	25	35	110	3.59	Accepted
Disagreed (2)	5	5	0	10		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	0	5	5		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The question of whether pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees, the table above also displayed 225 strongly agreed that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees with 110 respondents agreed that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees. However, 10 respondents disagreed that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees while 5 respondents strongly disagreed that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees. The mean score of 3.59 signifies that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees.

Table 6: Accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	70	30	50	150		
Agreed (3)	70	30	50	150	3.23	Accepted
Disagreed (2)	5	10	15	30		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	5	10	5	20		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The table also revealed that 150 respondents strongly agreed that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension with 150 respondents agreed that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension. Meanwhile, 30 respondents disagreed that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension with 20 respondents strongly disagreed that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension. By virtue of the mean score of 3.23, it indicates that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension.

Table 7: Accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	90	30	60	180		
Agreed (3)	40	35	50	125	3.33	Accepted
Disagreed (2)	10	10	5	25		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	10	5	5	20		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

On whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service, 180 respondents strongly agreed that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service, with 125 respondents agreed that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service. While 25 respondents disagreed that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service with 20 respondents

strongly disagreed that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service. The mean value of 3.33 implies that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service.

Table 8: Pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA).

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	140	30	70	240	3.57	Accepted
Agreed (3)	10	40	30	80		
Disagreed (2)	0	5	15	20		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	5	5	10		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

On whether pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA), the table above shows that 240 respondents strongly agreed that pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA) with 80 respondents agreed that pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA). 20 respondents disagreed that pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA) with 10 respondents state that pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA). The mean score of 3.57 accepted the fact that pension scheme enables retirees to access the Retirement Savings Account (RSA).

Table 9: Pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	100	30	60	190	3.47	Accepted
Agreed (3)	45	45	55	145		
Disagreed (2)	5	0	0	5		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	5	5	10		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The question of whether pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service, the table above also displayed 190 strongly agreed that pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service with 145 respondents agreed that pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service. However, 5 respondents disagreed that pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service while 10 respondents strongly disagreed that pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service. The mean score for this response is 3.47 and this indicated that pension administrators are transparent in the welfare management of retirees in the Service.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between fiscal responsibility, effectiveness of pension fund management policies and the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024

Item 1 of Research Question which states that “pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees” was employed with chi-square (X^2) thus: $X^2 = \sum \frac{(fo-fe)^2}{fe}$

Table 10: shows responses for calculating frequency expected (fe)

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response
Strongly Agreed (SA)	95	50	80	225
Agreed (A)	50	25	35	110
Disagreed (D)	5	5	0	10
Strongly Disagreed (SD)	0	0	5	5
Total	150	80	120	350

Source: Survey Data, 2025

$$fe = \frac{\text{Column total} \times \text{Row total}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 11: Computation of Chi-Square Test Statistics 1

FO	FE	FO – FE	(FO – FE) ²	(FO – FE) ² /FE
95	96	-1	9216	96
50	47	3	9	0.2
80	4	76	5776	1444
50	2	48	2304	1152
25	51	-26	676	13.3
35	25	10	100	4
5	2	3	9	4.5
5	1	4	16	16
0	77	-77	5929	77
0	38	-38	1444	38
0	3	-3	9	3
5	1	4	16	16
350	350			2864

X² Cal = 2864

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Tabulated at 0.05 level of significance

Hence, df = (R – 1) (C – 1)

Where:

R – number of rows,

C = number of columns

$$= (4 - 1) (3 - 1)$$

$$= (3) (2) = 6$$

From the above analysis,

df = 6

level of significance = 0.05% while

Chi-Square (X^2) = 2864

Table Value = 12.59

Decision Rule: The null hypothesis is rejected if chi-square (X^2) value is higher than the table value. Here, the chi-square value = 2864 and the table value = 12.59. It therefore signifies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the effectiveness of pension fund management policies and the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024 is rejected. This, in other words, means that, there is a significant relationship between the effectiveness of pension fund management policies and the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The effectiveness of fiscal responsibility and pension fund policies on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 – 2024.

Data analysis revealed that 335 respondents agreed that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees. The mean score of 3.59 signifies that pension administrators account for pension funds to retirees. The table also revealed that 300 respondents agreed that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension. By virtue of the mean score of 3.23, it indicates that accountability assures or guarantees retirees of regular payment of pension. On whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service, 305 respondents agreed that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service. The mean value of 3.33 implies that whether accountability fosters integrity in welfare management of retirees in the Service.

The views of the respondents were corroborated by Negbe and Egobueze (2021) who argued that “pension policies significantly accounted for retirees’ welfare in Rivers State”. Ngo, Egobueze and Nwaoburu (2024), noted that the Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS) aimed at improving financial security in retirement, with strong accountability crusade but challenges remain. Ajieh (2014), claimed that the CPS was designed to address shortcomings of the old defined benefit scheme, accountability, transparency, delays in payment and administrative issues continue to create insecurity and hardship for retirees. In line with this submission, a participant noted that:

Pension policies have projected some levels of accountability and transparency which translates to integrity in the management of the scheme. Pension policies aimed to strengthen the management and disbursement process, directed towards socioeconomic welfare and improvement of retirees. To me, there is a reasonable level of accountability and transparency in the management of pension funds as it concerns welfare of retirees (B. Osarolube, personal communication, January 20, 2025).

The above response affirmed the argument of Nwagwu (2014), that:

The Pension Reform Act 2004 identifies integrity, transparency and accountability among core values or founding principles for pension fund administration hence the need for probity, impartiality, fairness, honesty and truthfulness. These features were lacking in the old pension scheme which resulted in its ineffectiveness and unsustainability (p.5).

The findings show that pension fund administrators and custodians demonstrated transparency and accountability in managing pension funds, particularly in reporting to PENCOM. However, they did not extend this transparency to retirees, who are their primary clients. Alabandan (2011) recommended that transparency should include disclosure of investment returns and sharing formulas, possibly through annual general meetings involving all stakeholders. Additionally, he advised that pension funds should be insured against economic downturns to protect beneficiaries.

Moreover, 320 respondents agreed that the pension scheme allows retirees to access their Retirement Savings Account (RSA), with a mean score of 3.57. Regarding the transparency of pension administrators in managing retirees' welfare, 335 respondents felt they are transparent, with a mean score of 3.47. This indicates that pension management generally facilitates retirees' access to their savings, contributing to their socioeconomic welfare.

Tonks (2005) explains that the Pension Reforms Act (PRA) 2004 established a contributory scheme managed by private Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs), funded through individual contributions. He emphasizes that retirees need strong investment skills, which they develop through information processing, and that pooling funds under a single manager can lead to economies of scale, making management more efficient.

The study also shows a positive perception regarding the timeliness of pension payments. Many respondents believe the Contributory Pension Scheme effectively ensures prompt pension payments. This aligns with Chidi (2017), who identified the scheme as a significant improvement in addressing payment delays. Overall, the scheme has made notable progress in ensuring pensioners receive their benefits on time.

Another participant who supported this position noted that:

There are some levels of effectiveness in the management of pension policies in Rivers State. However, the issue of timely payment of monthly pension is still a burden which the Pension Board must tackle. When there is late payment, retirees may have no option than to borrow and pay back with interest whenever pensions are paid. At the end, our take home becomes very poor. (Buduuka, personal communication, January 20, 2025).

Ezenwa (2024) notes that many Nigerian workers remain skeptical about the pension scheme's success due to past failures with earlier programs. Some retirees lack a reliable pension because employers failed to enroll them or remit contributions properly. Improving systems for tracking and monitoring payments, and addressing discrepancies, could enhance retirees' confidence in the accuracy and reliability of benefits. Ngo, Egobueze, and Nwaoburu (2024) highlight concerns over the perceived ineffectiveness of measures to resolve pension payment delays, emphasizing the need for better strategies and proactive solutions.

Negbe and Egobueze (2021) observe that, in Rivers State, the pension system is generally viewed as effective in ensuring timely payments. However, issues such as corruption, inadequate funding, inconsistent payments, and ineffective delay mitigation remain. Addressing transparency, anti-corruption efforts, funding levels, and refining delay management can improve pension processes and bolster retirees' welfare.

Abanyam (2013) emphasizes that many Nigerian retirees suffer health deterioration after retirement, often due to pension management failures. Proper pension administration is crucial for the well-being of pensioners worldwide, but in Nigeria, maladministration has negatively impacted their health and quality of life. Delays and reductions in pension payments have led to financial hardship, contributing to declining health among retirees. These ongoing challenges reflect the difficult post-retirement experiences faced by many Nigerian pensioners. In a sharp reaction to the level of effective of the implementation of pension fund management, another participant revealed that:

When timely results are not achieved, there is no effectiveness. How can someone who have serve the state meritoriously, retired, get back home to rest, hoping for monthly stipends only to be delayed for no justifiable reason. This is the height of irresponsibility to senior citizens. We have been relegated to beggary. We have virtually become beggars. What effect are you asking; the poor attitude or the ill-treatment or delay payment? (Wechie, personal communication, January 20, 2025).

Most respondents emphasized that the rising incidence of illness and mortality among pensioners is largely driven by delays in pension payments and inadequate treatment. These concerns are closely linked to the mismanagement and poor administration of pensions in Nigeria, which includes issues like pension diversion and reductions by agents of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (Etuk, 2022). This highlights that establishing a pension commission alone is insufficient; without proper oversight and commitment, the health and well-being of retirees remain at risk. Failure to remit pensions promptly continues to exacerbate health problems among pensioners, undermining their welfare. Another participant reacted as follows:

There is no degree of efficiency and effectiveness anywhere in the management of our pension. I expect verification to go digital other than manual. This rigorous process of queuing up with some of us full of age has subdued many of us into unnecessary stress without due regard accorded us by pension managers. To me, the entire process is encumbered in nullity (W. Senibo, personal communication, January 20, 2025).

Most respondents noted that increasing illness and death among pensioners result from delays in payments and poor treatment. These issues stem from mismanagement and weak administration of pensions in Nigeria, including pension diversion and reductions by agents of the government (Etuk, 2022). Merely creating a pension commission is not enough; without effective oversight and dedication, retirees' health and welfare remain vulnerable. Delays in pension remittance worsen health conditions, further endangering their well-being.

CONCLUSION

This study examined how pension management policies influence the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State from 2014 to 2024. The findings indicate that ineffective policies hinder efficient pension administration, largely due to poor accountability among administrators, irregular disbursements, and procedural inefficiencies. Challenges such as bureaucratic delays, dishonesty, outdated systems, network failures, and weak oversight significantly undermine pension management and retirees' well-being. The current system fails to fully meet retirees' needs, necessitating reforms to eliminate political interference, enhance transparency, boost accountability, and foster investor confidence. Implementing these changes can improve retirees' living standards and ensure sustainable pension systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Rivers State government should collaborate with the pension board to establish a quality assurance unit and adopt innovative management approaches, including computerized processing, to improve efficiency and responsiveness.
2. An independent supervisory body should be appointed to oversee pension management, enforce transparency, and conduct regular audits.
3. Upgrade financial and administrative platforms with secure digital systems to streamline access, record-keeping, and reduce delays.
4. Facilitate regular communication channels between pension administrators, officials, and retirees through town halls, feedback systems, and awareness programs to build trust and transparency.

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